

Rural Marketing: Opportunities, Challenges and Practices in India

Ritesh Dalwadi*

Dr. J. A. Sethi*

Rajesh Patel*

NSVKMS MBA COLLEGE, VISNAGAR

Affiliated to Hemchandracharya North Gujarat University

E-mail: rbdalwadi11@yahoo.co.in

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* *The author is Faculty member, Nootan Sarva Vidyalaya Kelavani Mandal Sanchalit, MBA College, Visnagar (Hemchandracharya North Gujarat University).*

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Abstract

The marketplace is one of the few areas in modern society where people participate in a straight line today. Marketing is defined, as the process of defining, creating and fulfilling the consumers' needs better than competitors and knowledge of consumer behavior is therefore vital for achieving the marketing goals. Companies are found with newer ideas, business approaches and marketing philosophies, one of them is buzz among marketing practices, known as rural marketing. Rural marketing involves delivering manufactured or processed inputs or services to rural producers or consumers. Firms are targeting the rural consumers, who seem critical for the survival of tomorrow and success. Different companies adapt various strategies from helping rural consumers in needs identification - to - creation of value - to - distribution - to - after sales services and many other things. Companies have targeted to rural market and accepted rural marketing practices because the Indian rural market offers enormous opportunities and potential market for companies to explore.

In recent time, rural markets have acquired significance, as the overall growth of the economy has resulted into substantial increase in the purchasing power of the rural communities. On account of green revolution, white revolution and like, the rural areas are consuming a large quantity of industrial and urban manufactured products. In this context, a special marketing strategy, namely, *rural marketing* has emerged. The purpose of this paper is to bring out understanding of the Indian rural market, trace the significance of rural market, opportunities and challenges and to discuss how firms in India have used it. This paper cites various examples of how organizations today dedicating much attention to tap the Indian rural market and strategies. It is based on secondary data and literature study.

Introduction: Rural Marketing & Market

Before fifteen years, overseas consumer products were scarce in India and only available to the affluent. Import restrictions prevented or severely hindered foreign consumer goods from entrance to India. With the economic liberalization that ensued, foreign brands are now prevalent across India (Luce, 2002). Today, multinational corporations view emerging markets such as India as prime opportunities for growth. With a rural population equal to just under 2.5 times the population of the entire United States as of the 2000 census, the potential consumer base is astounding¹. But generally speaking, success in India's rural markets for multinational corporations has been mediocre at best. It is from these struggles and failures, however, that multinational corporations seeking to enter the rural Indian market can learn how to do so more wisely.

Rural marketing facilitate flow of goods and service from rural producers to urban consumers at possible time with reasonable prices, and agriculture inputs/ consumer goods from urban to rural. Marketing is an exchange function; it was started much earlier when civilization started but not recognized as marketing. All economy goods are marketed in terms of goods and services (Barter system). Now money is being practiced as a good exchanging medium. The surplus produce has been brought to sophisticated places where both buyers and sellers meet together and exchange goods, services and ideas in terms of money. The market may be a street, or a small town/ metropolitan city. Developments in infrastructure, transport, and communication facilities increased the scope of the rural market.

The broad emerging profile of rural marketing indicates the future of marketing in rural markets is full of opportunities, potential and challenges. In the coming future, the rural

¹ According to Shanthi Kanaan, writer for The Hindu, rural markets are growing twice as fast as the urban markets (2001)

markets and rural consumers will play a vital role in the success of business firms. In order to understand the expectations and aspirations of rural consumers, the business practitioners, marketers, marketing scientists and scholars, all are putting great efforts.

For quite some time now, the lure of rural India been the subject of animated discussion in corporate suites. And with good reason too. With urban markets getting saturated for several categories of consumer goods and with rising rural incomes, marketing executives are fanning out and discovering the strengths of the large rural markets as they try to enlarge their markets. Today, the idea has grown out of its infancy and dominates discussions in any corporate boardroom strategy session. Adi Godrej, chairman of the Godrej group that is in a range of businesses from real estate and personal care to agri-foods, has no hesitation proclaiming, “It is a myth that rural consumers are not brand and quality conscious².”

With a population already in excess of one billion people, India has caught the eye of multinational corporations across the globe as a place of opportunity for exploring new markets. While India has portions of their population that would be considered wealthy or middle class by Western standards, a much greater percentage of India’s population is low income. As a result, they spend money, live, and use products differently than the countries where most multinational corporations originate (Prahalad Lieberthal, 2003). Rural areas, in particular, exemplify these differences. Understanding the characteristics that make the people and the market in rural India unique can help corporations to enter this market with success. The key characteristics define the term *rural*, determine the amount and flow of income, and determine the types of products and packages that are typically used in rural India.

² Said by Adi Godrej, chairman of the Godrej group.

Opportunities and Challenges: Rural Marketing

Rural markets, as part of any economy, have untapped potential. There are several difficulties confronting the effort to fully explore rural markets. The concept of rural markets in India is still in evolving shape, and the sector creates a variety of opportunities and challenges. Rural market has following arrived and the following facts substantiate this.

- 742 million people
- Estimated annual size of the rural market
 - FMCG Rs 65,000 Crore
 - Durables Rs 5,000 Crore
 - Agri-inputs (incl. tractors) Rs 45,000 Crore
 - 2 / 4 wheelers Rs 8,000 Crore
- In 2001-02, LIC³ sold 55 % of its policies in rural India.
- Of two million BSNL⁴ mobile connections, 50% in small towns/villages.
- Of the six lakh villages, 5.22 lakh have a Village Public Telephone (VPT)
- 41 million Kisan Credit Cards issued (against 22 million credit-plus-debit cards in urban) with cumulative credit of Rs 977 billion resulting in tremendous liquidity.
- Of 20 million Rediffmail signups, 60 % are from small towns. 50% transactions from these towns on Rediff online shopping site

³ Life Insurance Corporation of India is the full name of LIC, Today LIC functions with 2048 fully computerized branch offices, 100 divisional offices, 7 zonal offices and the Corporate office.

⁴ Bharat Sanchar Nigam Ltd. formed in October, 2000, is World's 7th largest Telecommunications Company providing comprehensive range of telecom services in India: Wireline, CDMA mobile, GSM Mobile, Internet, Broadband, Carrier service, MPLS-VPN, VSAT, VoIP services, IN Services etc.

- 42 million rural HH⁵s availing banking services in comparison to 27 million urban HHs.
- Investment in formal savings instruments: 6.6 million HHs in rural and 6.7 million in urban
- Infrastructure is improving rapidly.
 - In 50 years only 40% villages connected by road, in next 10 years another 30%.
 - More than 90 % villages electrified, though only 44% rural homes have electric connections.
 - Rural telephone density has gone up by 300% in the last 10 years; STD connects every 1000+ pop.
- Social Indicators have improved a lot between 1981 and 2001
 - Number of “pacca” houses doubled from 22% to 41% and “kaccha” houses halved (41% to 23%)
 - Percentage of BPL⁶ families declined from 46% to 27%
 - Rural Literacy level improved from 36% to 59%
- Low penetration rates in rural so there are many marketing opportunities.

Durables	Urban	Rural	Total (% of rural HH)
CTV	30.4	4.8	12.1
Refrigerator	33.5	3.5	12.0

⁵ HH stands for the Households.

⁶ BPL stands for the Belo Poverty Line.

FMCGs	Urban	Rural	Total (% of rural HH)
Shampoo	66.3	35.2	44.2
Toothpaste	82.2	44.9	55.6

□ Marketers can make effective use of the large available infrastructure

- Post offices 1,38,000
- Haats (periodic markets) 42,000
- Melas (exhibitions) 25,000
- Mandis (agri markets) 7,000
- Public distribution shops 3,80,000
- Bank branches 32,000

While the rural market certainly offers a big attraction to marketers, it would be naive to think that any company can easily enter the market and walk away with a sizable market share. Actually the market bristles with a variety of challenges.

The troubles of physical distribution and channel management adversely affect the service as well as the cost aspect. The existent market structure consists of primary rural market and retail sales outlet. The structure involves stock points in feeder towns to service these retail outlets at the village levels. But it becomes difficult maintaining the required service level in the delivery of the product at retail level. One way could be using company delivery vans which can serve two purposes- it can take the products to the customers in every nook and corner of the market, and it also enables the firm to establish direct contact with them thereby facilitating sales promotion. However, only the bigwigs can adopt this channel. The companies with relatively fewer resources can go in for syndicated distribution where a tie-up between non-competitive marketers can be established to facilitate distribution.

In the area of communication, companies have perhaps failed to recognize that a rural consumer may be buying a particular brand or even the product category itself (particularly durables) for the first time. With hardly any key influencer within the village and few sources of information (since print and electronic media have limited reach), the rural consumer feels inhibited and ill equipped to buy confidently.

To communicate effectively with rural audiences, it is important to understand the aspirations, fears and hopes of rural customers, in relation to each product category, before developing a communication package to deliver the product message. Hence, there is a strong need to build reassurance and trust about product quality, service support and company credentials in the minds of rural consumers. This is best done through the face-to-face 'below the line' touch, feel and talk mode at haats, melas and mandis.

Language and regional behavior variations should be considered while developing rural communications strategy. Advertising and Public Relations agencies should entrust development of rural communications packages to professionals hailing from small towns, as they would have a better connect with rural mindset.

Although the reach of television in rural India is high, frequent power-cuts restrict viewing time considerably. With the licensing of FM channels to cover all district headquarters, the power of radio to deliver a localized message in a local language will soon be available to advertisers as a cost-effective way to reach rural masses. Rural India has a very high ownership of transistor radios and as these run on batteries, radio can once again be expected to become a popular medium for reaching rural masses.

As a general rule, rural marketing involves more intensive personal selling efforts compared to urban marketing. Companies need to understand the psyche of the rural consumers and then act accordingly. To effectively tap the rural market, a company must associate itself with the same things the rural community does. This can be achieved by utilizing the various media in rural areas to reach out to their readers in their own language and in large numbers, so that the brand can be associated with the myriad rituals, celebrations, festivals, meals and other activities where they assemble.

Rural Marketing: Practices in India

1) ITC – E-Choupals

Indian Tobacco Company (ITC) is one of the fastest growing FMCG companies of India, which launched an initiative called ‘e-choupal’, or Electronic Choupal as part of its social responsibility concerns. The e-choupal through its operators called “Sanchalaks” and “Samyojaks” broadly offer the following facilities to the farmers –

- ❑ Information on weather forecasts, market prices for grains etc., all news affecting agriculture.
- ❑ Best practices on farming, equipments, and risk management.
- ❑ Information regarding sources of agri-input supplies and also about consumer goods.
- ❑ Information about where to sell the agricultural produce.

In this way E-Choupal provides real-time information and customized knowledge by enhancing the ability of farmers to take decisions and align their farm output with market demand and secure quality & productivity. The aggregation of the demand for farm inputs from individual farmers gives them access to high quality inputs from established and reputed manufacturers at fair prices.

As a direct marketing channel, virtually linked to the 'mandi' system for price discovery, 'e-Choupal' eliminates wasteful intermediation and multiple handling. Thereby it significantly reduces transaction costs. Launched in June 2000, 'e-Choupal', has become the largest initiative among all Internet-based interventions in rural India. 'e-Choupal' services today reach out to more than 3.5 million farmers growing a range of crops - soyabean, coffee, wheat, rice, pulses, shrimp - in over 31,000 villages through 5372 kiosks across seven states (Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan and Kerala). Each of these kiosks are supposed to achieve a break-even in an year, which they generally do and after that the operation is profitable on a standalone basis.

2) HLL- Rural Market Initiatives

HLL has undertaken a number of projects in order to improve the might of the rural consumers hence creating a large customer base of it. Some of these initiatives are:

- ❑ **Project Shakti:** Aimed at empowering the rural women by providing a sustainable micro enterprise opportunity to them in order to improve rural living standards through health and hygiene awareness. Under this scheme a typical Shakti entrepreneur conducts a steady business by selling products of HLL, which gives her an income in excess of Rs. 1,000 per month.
- ❑ **Project Bharat:** It was launched in the year 1998-99. Under this project HLL vans visited villages and sold small packs consisting of a low unit price pack consisting each of its detergent, toothpaste, face cream and talcum powder for Rs. 15. The customers were shown the videos regarding how to use the products and how the use of company's products is beneficial for them as compared to their current habits.

- **Project Millennium:** It is targeted to tap the tea-vendors (chai-ki-dukan) in order to sell them the branded tea at a small price and packet size in order to improve the sale.

3) AMUL – DISK Project

The Amul⁷ model of co-operative farming represents a system that is collectively owned, operated and controlled by the farmers. It is an integrated 3-tier organized structure that procures, processes and markets the produce. The 3-tiers involved in the model of dairy farming includes village societies, district milk unions and the milk federations. This model removes the irrationalities of the traditional model where the processing and marketing was done by the middlemen, leading to major diversion of profit of the hard-earned labor of the farmer. Amul is able to do all this with the support of an ongoing project named the DISK project, which comprises of computerization of more than 70,000 village societies and automation of the milk collection process. The salient features of this project are described below.

Dairy Information System Kiosk (DISK) project

The DISK project as conceived by Amul has two components:

- An application running at the society level that could be provided with internet connectivity and,
- A dairy portal at the district level serving transactional and informational needs of all members and staff in the district co-operative structure.

The software developed for the society is able to provide

⁷ Amul (Anand Milk-producers Union Limited), formed in 1946, is a dairy cooperative movement in India. It is a brand name managed by an apex cooperative organisation, Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation Ltd. (GCMMF), which today is jointly owned by some 2.41 million milk producers in Gujarat, India.

- a) Data analysis and decision support to help a rural milk collection society in improving its performance, i.e. increasing milk collection.
- b) Data analysis to improve productivity and yield of cattle milk.
- c) Farmers with facilities to place orders for goods and services offered by different agencies in the co-operative sector and seek information on subjects of interest.

The services offered by each of the centers include

- ❑ Delivery of all sorts of information related with dairying.
- ❑ Access to a multimedia database on innovations captured by Shristi⁸.
- ❑ Facilities of communication like E-mail, fax, Internet Banking services, ATMs.
- ❑ Providing facility to farmers to download government forms, receive documents etc.
- ❑ Automatic printing of daily payment slips for farmers

In this way it acts as a complete solution provider for the rural farmers engaged in the dairying business by leveraging Information Technology in the best way.

⁸ Shristi is an NGO working on innovations with Indian Institute of Management – Ahmedabad.

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